

ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS ON "ROBOTICS" ON THE BASIS OF THE CREDIT SYSTEM

Siddikov Ilhomjon Hakimovich¹

Authors: Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor

Mullajonov Bahodirjon Arabboyevich²

¹⁻²Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi; Researcher Uzbek University of Journalism and Mass Communications.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6652089>

Annotation

This paper examines the organization of independent work of students on the topic of "robotics" on the basis of the credit system. Robotic devices were also analyzed on the example of Arduino, and suggestions and recommendations were made to further develop students' skills in working with these devices during independent work.

Keywords: Credit system, robotics, microcontroller, Arduino, independent work
Today, information technology has penetrated into all spheres of our lives and has become an integral part of it. In particular, the introduction of modern information technologies in the field of education allows to organize the teaching process and the teaching process on the basis of new approaches. This speeds up the learning process and makes it better. Information technology is a way of processing information through various hardware and software devices. When it comes to information technology, it is impossible not to mention the concept of robotics. Robotics is the most powerful and multifunctional field ever created by man. [4,12] More and more robots are providing services, and our work is becoming easier.

The field of robotics is developing day by day and is entering all areas. This paper examines the use of robotics in the educational process, using modern advances in the field of robotics, the study of robotics in the process of independent learning using the Arduino device. Independent education also plays an important role in training future professionals.

In 1999, 29 countries signed the Declaration on Participation in the Creation of a Unified Educational Environment in Bologna. Its goal is to adopt a system of comparable degrees, facilitate academic and professional recognition, and provide employment opportunities for graduates. The Bologna process is open to all countries, and today the number of participating states is close to 50. All countries that have signed the Bologna Declaration have moved to a two-stage system of higher education (bachelor - 3-4 years, master - 1-2 years). After higher education, it is possible to obtain a doctorate (3-4 years). [2,30]

So what does a credit-module system mean? Today, the practice of the so-called credit system is widely used in the world to implement educational programs. The credit system includes 5 tuition fees and the total labor costs for it. In the world practice, the most common are the United States Credit System (USCS),

the British Credit Collection and Transfer System (SATS), the European Credit System (ECTS), and the Asia-Pacific System for University Loans (UCTS). systems. The credit hour system originated in the United States and has evolved. [6,36]

To date, almost all European countries have reformed their national higher education systems and introduced credit education. However, they differ significantly because they focus on national socio-economic issues. Each country has tried to preserve its unique education system, national, historical and cultural traditions. [5,62]

Mankind has always tried its best to make daily life and work easier, and this has led to the emergence of a class of machines called robots. It was a whole field of robotics. One of the most actively developed countries in this field is Japan. Scientists hope that in the next decade, people will be as familiar as they are with the use of smartphones. [3,42]

Robotics is the study of the development of electronics, as well as mechanics and programming based on automated technical systems. Robot manufacturing is one of the most advanced areas of modern industry. Imagine that today thousands of robots are working in factories and enterprises instead of human labor. [1,142]

Arduino is one of the most successful projects and platforms for free software and hardware with the greatest success and the greatest impact in the world. The community has created both open source software for microcontroller programming and a variety of free motherboards to work with. All are licensed under the GNU GPL, so that many applications and their derivatives can be created.

The Arduino platform is a set of built-in printed circuit boards. The Arduino can be used both to create autonomous automation facilities and to connect applications on a computer via standard wired and wireless interfaces.

We recommend that students use the Arduino platform to organize their independent work on the subject of "robotics". The main reasons for this are:

- Arduino controllers are much cheaper than other similar devices;
- Multi-function;
- Ease of learning;
- The breadth of opportunities to create new devices;
- Very compact in size;
- And many other benefits.

References:

1. Sandeep Musale et al., "Smart reader for visually impaired", 2018 2nd International Conference on Inventive Systems and Control (ICISC).
2. Tojiev M. Mamadaliev K. Khurramov A. The role and importance of the credit system in the development of higher education in developed

- countries. Prospects for the development of higher education: collection №3. Tashkent 2015. 52-p.
3. Nazarov X.N. Intellectual multi-coordinate mechatronic modules of robotic systems. Tashkent. TGTU, 2019 131 s.
 4. Nazarov X.N. Robotics systems and complexes. T. Economics and finance. 2016. -706 b.
 5. Usmonov B.Sh., Khabibullaev R.A. Organization of the educational process in higher education institutions in the credit-module system. Study guide. T.: Tafakkur Publishing House, 2020. 120 bet.
 6. Urinov V. ECTS credit-module system in higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan: basic concepts and rules. Study guide. New Brunswick University, 2020 y.

